

MENTAL HEALTH LITERACY AMONG EMPLOYEES OF A STATE UNIVERSITY: TOWARDS A PROPOSED WELLNESS PROGRAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 2

Pages: 267-290

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2850

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14603043

Manuscript Accepted: 12-06-2024

Mental Health Literacy among Employees of a State University: Towards a Proposed Wellness Program

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Abstract

Mental health literacy is considered a prerequisite for the early recognition and treatment of mental health conditions. Assessing this concept is fundamental in identifying knowledge gaps and misconceptions about mental health, as well as in the development and evaluation of interventions to promote it. This study aimed to measure mental health literacy among employees of Tarlac State University and to compare this literacy across different demographic groups. It employed a descriptive-comparative research design, using a researcher-developed Mental Health Literacy Survey to gather data from two hundred and eleven (211) participants. Findings revealed that respondents were knowledgeable across all domains of mental health literacy. Significant influences of respondents' age, position, education, and training on certain aspects of their mental health literacy were observed, but no significant influence was found based on sex. Specifically, different age groups displayed varying abilities to recognize mental health problems, understand risk factors and causes, and exhibit attitudes that promote appropriate help-seeking behavior. Position within the organization significantly influences attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behaviors. Educational attainment significantly affected knowledge of risk factors and causes, as well as information-seeking knowledge. Attendance at training related to mental health significantly improved all domains of mental health literacy, except for the ability to recognize mental health problems. Based on these conclusions, the following recommendations are made to strengthen the institution's wellness program: continuation of mental health literacy education, enhancement of the promotion of university mental health services, customized training programs for each demographic group, capacity-building for supervisors and mental health professionals, formation of support and interest groups, establishment of an employee welfare unit and mental health committee, review of working conditions, and provision of facilities dedicated to employee welfare.

Keywords: *mental health, employees, wellness, program*

Introduction

“Take care of your body. It’s the only place you have to live.” - Jim Rohn.

This passage serves as a stark reminder that in our fast-paced world, where individuals often find themselves making sacrifices to keep up, health must not be compromised. In today’s society, busyness is glorified, almost as if it’s a badge of honor, importance, and self-worth. It has become the norm for people to juggle multiple roles, responsibilities, projects, and schedules due to the mounting pressure to excel in various areas, including profession, family life, and personal development. At some point, the line between life and work became blurred.

Unfortunately, this idea has not only permeated individuals but has also extended to institutions in society, ultimately leading to a generation grappling with burnout. Guilaran, in his 2024 article “On the Wellbeing of University Faculty,” emphasized how higher education in the Philippines has become progressively aggressive in meeting the changing global demand for talent, to the extent that it inadvertently led to an increase in academic burnout (Dinibutun et al., 2020 & Sabagh et al., 2018). The quest for global recognition, mirrored in various accreditations and the chase for national and international rankings, has propelled staff at state universities to deliver superior instruction, research, and services. While this pursuit of excellence is generally commendable, its negative effect on employee welfare was unexpected.

This is concerning, as academic burnout can trigger underlying medical and mental issues that can lead to depression, anxiety, eating and panic disorders, substance misuse, addiction, and other mental health problems. What is more troubling is that despite this prevalent occupational sickness, discussions on mental health remain largely stigmatized. Even amidst the significant advancements in legislation, such as the passage of RA 11036 or the Mental Health Act of 2018, which mandated all employers in the country to develop appropriate policies and programs on mental health, the implementation of these services in state universities appears to be lacking. The systemic flaws exposed during the pandemic serve as a testament to this inadequacy. While many faculty and personnel struggled to stay afloat while rapidly transitioning to remote modalities of teaching, research, and public service—meeting demands from both students and administration and navigating the challenges of sickness and death during the COVID-19 pandemic—it became evident that while there is a process in place to ensure student well-being, those intended for employees were insufficient. For example, while students have access to guidance services, faculty and personnel struggle to seek professional help to address their mental health difficulties within the university (Guilaran, 2024).

Workplace counseling, a specialized branch of guidance and counseling often referred to as employee counseling or mental health assistance, is a supportive initiative designed to address various challenges and promote well-being among staff members within an

organization. It offers a range of services to assist employees in handling personal and work-related matters that could affect their mental health, job performance, and overall quality of life. Its core purpose is to provide guidance, emotional support, and practical resources to help individuals navigate difficult circumstances and develop adaptive coping mechanisms. These situations may include stress, anxiety, burnout, substance abuse, family conflicts, and other personal challenges that can impact professional performance and productivity.

Employee counseling, provided through an Employee Assistance Program (EAP), includes both face-to-face counseling and a telephone-based helpline. These sessions primarily focus on problem-solving, where counselors assist clients in finding solutions to their life issues or developing more efficient ways of dealing with challenges. Unfortunately, as Mind Nation (2021) reports, most employee assistance programs in the country are generally underused and, at times, inaccessible. This is particularly evident in the research locale itself, where only a few clients sought the provided telecounseling service during the pandemic. In fact, the mental health services provided by Tarlac State University's Human Resource Development and Management Office through the Employee Assistance Program are generally underutilized.

This underutilization is concerning, especially since mental health issues have been cited, albeit not explicitly, as reasons for tardiness, low productivity, absences, and leave among employees at the research locale. The researcher observed that discussions around this topic are often limited and spoken in hushed tones, perpetuating stigma in the workplace. This stigma, as Rivera & Antonio (2017) point out, is the most significant barrier to developing a mental health system. It hinders open discussions on mental health, making it difficult for people to understand the issue.

To address this, the researcher proposes that the first step in strengthening the institution's wellness program is to gauge employees' mental health literacy in the areas of recognition, knowledge, and attitude. This is based on previous studies that revealed employees with high mental health literacy cope better with mental health difficulties (Simon & Mahinay, 2023; Cardinez & Mahinay, 2023). These findings suggest that literacy plays a crucial role in the effective management of a mental health program.

Mental health literacy was introduced and defined by Jorm and colleagues in 1997 as the knowledge and beliefs people have about mental disorders that aid in their recognition, management, or prevention. Over the past decades, research has focused on mental health literacy, as it is considered a prerequisite for the early recognition and treatment of mental disorders. Assessing this concept has become fundamental in identifying knowledge gaps and misconceptions regarding mental health issues, as well as in the development and evaluation of interventions to promote mental health.

However, despite being a topic of extensive global research, the mental health literacy of Filipinos remains unexplored and receives little attention. Recent studies have primarily focused on mental health itself, with only a few concentrating on mental health literacy and its relationship with Filipinos. The published literature is also insufficient in examining the mental health literacy of Filipino adults, specifically, those aged 40 to 65, as most studies conducted in the country, have largely centered on teenagers and young adults aged 13 to 35 years (Rey et al., 2022). To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no existing mental health literacy study in the Philippine setting has focused on the working group, particularly with the intent to address employees' mental health needs.

With the ever-increasing demands of academic life and the evolving discourse on mental health and welfare, the researcher is convinced that it is past time to give employees' mental health greater importance. Aligned with the University's mission of empowering human resources, it is imperative to examine employees' mental health literacy to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of wellness interventions and programs aimed at strengthening it. The faculty and personnel are the backbone of the University; therefore, their well-being should be a priority.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the mental health literacy among employees of a state university. Specifically, it addresses the following problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of Tarlac State University employees in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. position (teaching or non-teaching);
 - 1.4. educational background; and
 - 1.5. attendance to seminar/training related to mental health?
2. How can the mental health literacy of the respondents be described in terms of:
 - 2.1. ability to recognize mental health problems;
 - 2.2. knowledge of the risk factors and causes;
 - 2.3. knowledge of self-treatment;
 - 2.4. knowledge of where to seek information;
 - 2.5. knowledge of available professional help; and
 - 2.6. attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior?
3. How can the mental health literacy among the respondents be compared when they are grouped according to their profile?

4. What wellness program may be proposed based on the findings of the study?
5. What implications could this study have for guidance and counseling?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-comparative design, a methodology that entails the detailed documentation, analysis, and interpretation of the current state, structure, or processes of phenomena. The primary objective was to elucidate the extent of correlation among several variables, none of which were manipulated for the purpose of the study. The researcher conducted an in-depth examination of the similarities and differences among the various variables under consideration.

The researcher believes that this is the best strategy to adopt since the purpose of this study was to assess and describe the mental health literacy among employees of a state university in terms of their ability to recognize mental health problems, attitude toward mental illness stigma, knowledge of self-treatment, knowledge of where to seek information, knowledge of professional help, and attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior, and to evaluate how varied their literacy levels are when grouped by demographic profile.

Respondents

The focus of this research was the employees of Tarlac State University who were between the ages of 23 and 63, had at least graduated from an elementary level of education, could read and write, and had been employed in a plantilla (contractual, temporary, or permanent) position for at least a year. For a well-represented sample, the researcher utilized Stratified Random Sampling. The researcher divided the subjects into subgroups, also called strata, according to their position (non-teaching personnel or faculty), and then used Microsoft Excel for Simple Random Sampling. The number of respondents was determined using Cochran's Finite Formula.

Instrument

The researcher used a self-developed instrument called Mental Health Literacy Survey (MHLS) in this study. The MHLS contains questions about the respondent's demographic profile and a sixty (60) item scale-based assessment of a person's mental health literacy level based on their ability to recognize disorders, knowledge of where to find information, knowledge of risk factors and causes, knowledge of self-treatment, knowledge of professional help available, and attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behaviors. Sample items from the scale include "I think children don't experience mental health problems" and "I think seeing a mental health professional means you are not strong enough to manage your own difficulties". The overall score is computed by getting the mean of all the items together using a five (5) point Likert scale on the level of agreeance (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree) with the highest possible mean of 5 and lowest of 1. The higher the mean, the higher the mental health literacy of the individual. To reduce response bias, fifteen (15) items were reverse scored.

The Mental Health Literacy Survey was developed using Anthony F. Jorm's (2000) mental health literacy concept and components, which include disorder recognition (DR), risk factor knowledge (RFK), available professional help (APH), self-treatment knowledge (STK), information-seeking knowledge (ISK), and attitudes (A). These dimensions served as the conceptual framework, and based on this, the researcher independently constructed fifteen (15) benchmark statements for each subscale, with some inspired by O'Connor and Casey's Mental Health Literacy Scale (2015).

The validation process was carried out by a team of five experts. This team included two psychologists and three guidance counselors, with four of them also being experienced psychometricians in the field of psychological assessment. In terms of their educational background, four of the experts hold a bachelor's degree in psychology, two have a master's degree in psychology, three have a master's degree in guidance and counseling, and one has earned a doctorate in guidance and counseling. Each of these experts brings a wealth of experience to the table, having spent at least a decade validating psychological tests and research tools, as well as teaching major courses in counseling and psychology. Their collective expertise ensured a comprehensive and rigorous validation process.

In the initial validation, no item was rejected, but most were marked for revision due to the use of overly advanced language and terminologies for the target participants, as well as the need for rewording for political correctness and clarity. In the final validation, the validators unanimously decided to accept all ninety (90) items for all six subscales. The survey was then translated into Filipino with the help of a Filipino Language Specialist, to benefit participants who are not fluent in English.

A pilot test was then conducted with twenty-five (25) participants from the sample respondents—employees of Tarlac State University—via Google Form. Responses were recorded and analyzed, and through item-total statistics, sixty (60) items out of ninety (90) were retained. For the final items, the computed Content Validity Index was recorded at 0.92, signifying high validity, while internal consistency showed good to excellent reliability scores for all subscales: Disorder Recognition ($\alpha = 0.96$), Risk-Factor Knowledge ($\alpha = 0.85$), Available Professional Help ($\alpha = 0.81$), Self-Treatment Knowledge ($\alpha = 0.88$), Information-Seeking Knowledge ($\alpha = 0.89$), and Attitudes ($\alpha = 0.95$), and for the total scale ($\alpha = 0.96$) when assessed with Cronbach's Alpha. This suggests that the MHLS is a practical, valid, and reliable instrument for measuring Mental Health Literacy.

In addition, a separate section was included in the questionnaire to solicit employee feedback and suggestions for improving the institution's current mental health program.

Procedure

The researcher utilized an electronic survey using Google Forms as the online platform. Items of the Mental Health Literacy Survey were encoded into Google Forms with participant-informed consent. This method was deemed more practical than paper and pencil due to restrictions imposed by the government as a precaution against communicable diseases. However, considering that the participants of the current study comprised a large age group and diverse educational backgrounds, which may have limited their skills, knowledge, devices, and/or connectivity to access online platforms, a printed version of the survey questionnaire was made available for their convenience and preference.

The link to the electronic survey was sent through Microsoft Teams, while the printed copy was personally delivered with the agency's permission and in accordance with their health safety guidelines.

Data Analysis

To determine the respondents' profile, the collected data was subjected to statistical analysis using percentage distribution and frequency following the procedure outlined below:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where:

P = percentage

f = frequency

% = percentage

n = total number of respondents

For the respondents' level of mental health literacy, weighted mean was calculated using the formula:

Where:

W = weighted average

n = number of terms to be averaged

w_i = weights applied to x values

X_i = data values to be averaged

Finally, mental health literacy among respondents was compared when grouped according to profile using One-Factor ANOVA and t-test between independent data.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher obtained approval and permission from Tarlac State University through the Human Resource Development and Management Office and the Data Protection Office to conduct the study. A letter outlining the purpose, participant selection, procedures, benefits of the study, and addressing confidentiality, data management, and other concerns was provided to the participants. Data gathering began only after receiving their approval. Participation was explained to the respondents as completely optional and with no impact on their employment. Additionally, because some of the survey's questions could be sensitive, a debriefing section was included at the end. This section clarified the study's purpose and encouraged participants to seek help from a mental health professional if they felt uncomfortable. The debriefing section also included a list of mental health hotlines.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered from the respondents of the study. It details the demographic profile of the respondents and their mental health literacy.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profile provides the gathered information about the respondents' age, sex, position, educational attainment, and attendance to mental health-related training, to offer a better understanding of the sample's characteristics.

Age

In this study, age is the length of time the respondent has lived. It was categorized into four generations based on the classification of Pew Research Center (2019), specifically, the Baby Boomers (born 1946-1964), Generation X (born 1965-1980), Millennials (born 1981-1996), and Zoomers (born 1997-2012).

Each of these groups possesses attitudes and behaviors that are unique to their generation. Recognizing these differences is instrumental in understanding their respective perceptions and behaviors toward mental health.

Table 1. *Age Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
23 to 26	26	12.3
27 to 42	118	55.9
43 to 58	60	28.4
59 to 63	7	3.3
Total	211	100.0

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents were 27 to 42 years old, with a frequency of 118 or 55.9%, followed by ages 43 to 58, with a frequency of 60 or 28.4%; ages 23 to 26, with a frequency of 26 or 12.3%; and the smallest group, 59 to 63, with a frequency of 7 or 3.3%.

The primary respondents of this study are Millennials, also known as Generation Y, aged between 27 and 42. They are closely followed by Generation X employees, who fall in the age bracket of 43 to 58. The substantial presence of these groups is expected, given that they are currently in their peak working years.

On the other hand, Generation Z, or 'Zoomers', who are the youngest generation in the workforce and aged 23 to 26, are less represented. This could be attributed to the fact that many individuals in this age group are either still pursuing their education or have just started their professional careers.

Lastly, the Baby Boomers, who are aged between 59 and 63, have the least representation. This is likely because a considerable number of individuals in this age group are either nearing retirement or have already retired.

Sex

In this study, "sex" was classified into the biological assignment of the respondents as male or female. Identifying this demographic and recognizing their differences and similarities can aid in understanding their perceptions and behaviors toward mental health.

Table 2. *Sex Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Female	108	51.2
Male	103	48.8
Total	211	100.0

Table 2 displays that 51.2% of the respondents were female, with a frequency of 108, while 48.8% of the respondents with a frequency of 103 were male.

As a government institution, Tarlac State University is committed to the principles of Equal Employment Opportunity. It recognizes the importance of equality and diversity, ensuring that there is no discrimination based on gender identity or sexual orientation in its hiring practices. However, it is noteworthy that the university's total population has a higher number of males (326) than females (285). This is largely due to the predominance of males in certain roles such as engineering, information technology, security, utility, motor pool, and skilled labor. Interestingly, in this study, the number of female participants exceeded that of males, as sex was not a determining factor in the random sampling used.

Position (Teaching or Non-teaching)

In this study's demographic profiling, respondents were categorized according to their roles within the organization. Specifically, they were distinguished between teaching and non-teaching staff to provide a better understanding of their differences and similarities in knowledge and attitude toward mental health.

Table 3. *Position Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Teaching	119	56.4
Non-Teaching	92	43.6
Total	211	100.0

Table 3 illustrates that 56.4% of the respondents were teaching personnel, with a frequency of 119, while 43.6% of the respondents with a frequency of 92 were non-teaching personnel.

Teaching and non-teaching personnel play distinct but equally important roles in fostering an effective educational environment. The teaching personnel, typically referred to as faculty, are responsible for providing instruction alongside the conduct of research and extension services for the community. On the other hand, non-teaching personnel, also known as the non-academic staff, are responsible for the university's administrative, operational, and support functions, which include registrars, librarians, counselors, accountants, IT support, and janitors, among other human resources.

The University's programs and services for the two groups differ, such as working hours, vacation arrangements, academic assistance, professional development schemes and opportunities, and tenure arrangements, among other things, which may or may not have an impact on their mental health literacy.

Educational Attainment

Respondents were also categorized based on their educational level, ranging from primary to doctoral education, to determine if there were any significant differences in their knowledge and attitude toward mental health.

Table 4. Educational Attainment Profile of the Respondents

<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Elementary Graduate	1	0.5
High School Graduate	10	4.7
College Graduate	104	49.3
Master's Graduate	74	35.1
Doctorate Graduate	22	10.4
Total	211	100.0

Table 4 displays that 0.5% or 1 of the respondents was an elementary school graduate, 4.7% with a frequency of 10 were high school graduates, 49.3% with a frequency of 104 were college graduates, 35.1% with a frequency of 74 were master's graduate, and 10.4% with a frequency of 22 were doctorate graduate.

The study was conducted in a higher education institution, which is why most respondents held college degrees and pursued further education at the master's and doctoral levels. It's also worth noting that teaching personnel are required to obtain a master's degree as a condition for permanent employment. On the other hand, the educational requirements for non-teaching staff to achieve security of tenure are more flexible, with some roles only requiring a basic level of education. Nevertheless, attaining higher education can provide both teaching and non-teaching staff with more opportunities for higher-paying positions.

Attendance to Training Related to Mental Health

Finally, respondents were divided into those who had mental health training and those who had not, to determine if their participation influenced mental health literacy.

Table 5. Training Profile of the Respondents

<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
With training	174	82.5
Without training	37	17.5
Total	211	100.0

Table 5 demonstrates that 82.5% of the respondents with a frequency of 174 have participated in a mental health seminar or training, whereas 17.5% with a frequency of 37 have not.

Tarlac State University offers mental health-related training at no cost to all its staff members. Regrettably, some employees were unable to participate in these sessions for various reasons. Some faced scheduling conflicts, while others were simply unaware of these activities. Additionally, the predominance of online training posed a significant barrier for those lacking the necessary digital devices or stable internet connectivity, a challenge particularly pronounced among non-teaching employees, especially those in blue-collar jobs.

For teaching personnel, participation in such training is not only beneficial but mandatory, and it contributes to their performance evaluation at the end of each semester. In contrast, non-teaching personnel do not have the same performance evaluation criteria, which may have contributed to their lower participation rates.

Mental Health Literacy of the Respondents

Mental Health Literacy refers to the knowledge and beliefs about mental disorders that aid in their recognition, management, and prevention.

It encompasses the ability to recognize specific disorders or types of psychological distress, understanding of risk factors and causes, knowledge of self-help interventions, awareness of available professional help, attitudes that facilitate recognition and appropriate help-seeking, and knowledge of how to obtain mental health information (Jorm, 2000).

Ability to Recognize Mental Health Problems

The ability to recognize mental health problems refers to the awareness of and skill in identifying the signs and symptoms of a potential mental health problem, such as changes in appetite, sleeping pattern, perception, and/or behavior.

Table 6. Ability to Recognize Mental Health Problems

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
I think someone who hurts themselves and has suicidal thoughts may be dealing with a mental health condition (Sa tingin ko ang taong nananakit sa sarili at nag-iisip magpakamatay ay malamang na may kondisyon sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	4.53	0.61	Very Knowledgeable (VK)
I think someone is having a panic attack when they experience intense fear, a racing heart, sweating, and breathing difficulty even in the absence of a clear danger or trigger (Sa tingin ko ang isang tao ay malamang na nagkakaroon ng panic attack kapag nakararanas ng matinding takot, mabilis na pagtibok ng puso, pagpapawis, at kahirapan sa paghinga kahit na walang nakaambang panganib)	4.32	0.63	Knowledgeable (K)
I think someone is suffering from anxiety when they worry excessively about a variety of minor issues, struggle to control their worry, and display physical symptoms such as tense muscles and tiredness (Sa tingin ko ang taong may labis na pag-aalala sa maliliit na isyu, pakikipagbuno sa pagkontrol nito at may pisikal na sintomas gaya ng tension sa kalamnan at pagkapagod ay dumaranas ng pagkabalisa o anxiety)	4.27	0.63	Knowledgeable (K)
I think Bipolar Disorder is a mental health condition that causes extreme mood swings that include emotional highs (full of energy) and lows (sadness or hopelessness) (Sa tingin ko ang Bipolar Disorder ay isang kondisyon sa kalusugang pangkaisipan na nagdudulot ng matinding mood swings na kinabibilangan ng emotional highs (puno ng enerhiya) at lows (lungkot o kawalan ng pag-asa))	4.24	0.64	Knowledgeable (K)
I think Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder symptoms include disturbing memories, avoidance of thinking about or discussing the traumatic event, and changes in physical and emotional reactions (Sa tingin ko ang mga sintomas ng Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder ay kinabibilangan ng mga nakakagambalang alaala, pag-iwas sa pag-iisip at pagtatalakay ukol sa nakakahindik na pangyayari, at may mga pagbabagong pisikal at emosyonal)	4.23	0.64	Knowledgeable (K)
I think people who have an excessive sense of self-importance, act arrogantly, and are unwilling to recognize the needs and feelings of others are likely to have a personality disorder (Sa tingin ko ang mga taong may labis na pagpapahalaga sa sarili, lubhang may kayabangan, at ayaw kumilala sa mga pangangailangan at damdamin ng iba ay masasabing may personality disorder)	4.03	0.72	Knowledgeable (K)
I think a person is likely to be experiencing major depression if they have a low mood for two weeks or more, lose enjoyment or interest in their normal activities, and have changes in their appetite and sleep (Sa tingin ko may nararanasang matinding depresyon ang taong may mababang mood sa loob ng dalawang lingo o mahigit pa, walang sigla o interes sa mga nakasanayang gawain at may mga pagbabago sa pagkagana at pagtulog)	3.98	0.80	Knowledgeable (K)
I think people who see themselves as fat despite having a low body weight, being afraid of gaining weight, and severely restricting food intake are likely to be dealing with a mental health condition (Sa tingin ko, ang mga taong nakikita ang kanilang sarili bilang mataba sa kabila ng pagkakaroon ng mababang timbang, nangangambang madagdagan ang timbang, at may matinding paghihigpit sa pagkain ay malamang na humaharap sa isang kondisyon sa kalusugan ng isip)	3.92	0.87	Knowledgeable (K)
I think impulsiveness, hyperactivity, and difficulty paying attention could be symptoms of a mental health condition (Sa tingin ko ang walang habas na pagdedesisyon, sobrang kalikutan, at kawalan ng konsentrasyon ay maaaring sintomas ng kondisyong pangkaisipan)	3.86	0.72	Knowledgeable (K)
I think an individual with an unhealthy fixation with cleanliness to the extent that hand washing makes their skin burn may be suffering from an obsessive-compulsive disorder (Sa tingin ko ang isang indibidwal na dumaranas ng Obsessive-Compulsive disorder ay hindi akma ang kalinisan kung kaya't nasusugat ang balat sa paghuhugas)	3.69	0.93	Knowledgeable (K)
	Overall Mean	4.11	Knowledgeable (K)

Table 6 reveals that the respondents are knowledgeable in recognizing mental health issues, with an overall mean of 4.11. The item with the highest mean score of 4.53 (and a standard deviation of 0.61), indicating a very knowledgeable understanding, is 'someone who hurts themselves and has suicidal thoughts may be dealing with a mental health condition. This is followed by several items. The item 'someone is having a panic attack when they experience intense fear, a racing heart, sweating, and breathing difficulty even in the absence of a clear danger or trigger' has a mean of 4.32 and a standard deviation of 0.63. The item 'someone is suffering from anxiety when they worry excessively about a variety of minor issues, struggle to control their worry, and display physical symptoms such as tense muscles and tiredness' has a mean of 4.27 and a standard deviation of 0.63. The item 'Bipolar Disorder is a mental health condition that causes extreme mood swings that include emotional highs (full of energy) and lows (sadness or hopelessness)' has a mean of 4.24 and a standard deviation of 0.64.

The item 'Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder symptoms include disturbing memories, avoidance of thinking about or discussing the

traumatic event, and changes in physical and emotional reactions' has a mean of 4.23 and a standard deviation of 0.64. The item 'people who have an excessive sense of self-importance, act arrogantly, and are unwilling to recognize the needs and feelings of others are likely to have a personality disorder' has a mean of 4.03 and a standard deviation of 0.72.

Other items also received knowledgeable ratings, albeit with lower mean scores. These include 'a person is likely to be experiencing major depression if they have a low mood for two weeks or more, lose enjoyment or interest in their normal activities, and have changes in their appetite and sleep' (mean of 3.98 and standard deviation of 0.80), 'people who see themselves as fat despite having a low body weight, being afraid of gaining weight, and severely restricting food intake are likely to be dealing with a mental health condition' (mean of 3.92 and standard deviation of 0.87), 'impulsiveness, hyperactivity, and difficulty paying attention could be symptoms of a mental health condition' (mean of 3.86 and standard deviation of 0.72), and 'an individual with an unhealthy fixation with cleanliness to the extent that hand washing makes their skin burn may be suffering from an Obsessive-Compulsive disorder' (mean of 3.69 and standard deviation of 0.93).

Building on this, the findings of this study align with the research conducted by Cardinez & Mahinay (2023) on Elementary School Teachers and Dizon (2019) on students of a state university in the Philippines. These studies collectively revealed a high level of literacy in recognizing mental health problems among the respondents. However, Dizon (2019) also highlighted that despite having adequate knowledge about mental health problems, respondents had a limited understanding of diagnosing these conditions based on the duration of symptoms. This mirrors the results of the current study, where items describing symptoms of Depression, Body Dysphoria, Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder, and Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder earned lower scores.

In essence, the data suggest that employees of Tarlac State University are most adept at identifying that individuals who self-harm and experience suicidal thoughts may be dealing with a mental health condition. This heightened awareness could be attributed to increased exposure to these conditions through media coverage, educational programs, or firsthand experiences, particularly after the enactment of the Mental Health Act (RA 11036) in 2018, and even more so amidst the pandemic. The alarming 57% surge in suicide cases, as reported by the Philippine Statistics Authority, coupled with a rise in suicide-related calls to the National Center for Mental Health, has prompted the community to open more spaces, particularly online, for mental health discussions. The portrayal of mental health illnesses in television shows and films has also increased, likely contributing to raising public awareness and reducing stigma associated with these conditions.

Knowledge of Risk-Factors and Causes

The knowledge of risk factors and causes refers to the understanding of the origins of mental health problems such as genetic makeup, environmental stressors, lifestyle choices, and physical health, among others.

Table 7. Knowledge of Risk-Factors and Causes

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
I think mental disorders are the result of both genetic and environmental factors (Sa tingin ko ang mga sakit pangkaisipan ay namana at dulot ng pangyayaring pangkapaligiran (trauma, pang-aabuso, stress))	4.35	0.74	Knowledgeable (K)
I think adult mental health can be strongly influenced by childhood trauma, abuse, or neglect (Sa tingin ko, ang kalusugang pangkaisipan ng mga nasa hustong gulang ay maaari pa ring maimpluwensyahan ng trauma, pang-aabuso, o pagpapabayang naranasan sa pagkabata)	4.30	0.67	Knowledgeable (K)
I think alcohol abuse can cause a wide range of mental health problems, including anxiety and depression (Sa tingin ko, ang pag-abuso sa alak ay maaaring magdulot ng malawakang problema sa kalusugang pangkaisipan kabilang ang pagkabalisa at depresyon)	4.25	0.75	Knowledgeable (K)
I think a head injury or a neurological condition like epilepsy can have an impact on your behavior and mood (Sa tingin ko ang isang kapinsalaan sa ulo o kondisyong neurological tulad ng epilepsy ay maaaring magkaroon ng epekto sa iyong pag-uugali at mood)	4.14	0.70	Knowledgeable (K)
I think people from loving, nurturing homes can also struggle with their mental health (Sa palagay ko, ang mga taong kahit nagmula sa mapagmahal at makalingang tahanan ay maaari ring makaranas ng sakit pangkaisipan)	4.06	0.77	Knowledgeable (K)
I think mental illness is a prevalent disability in the Philippines (Sa tingin ko ang sakit sa kaisipan ay isang lagapan na kapansanan sa Pilipinas)	3.89	0.86	Knowledgeable (K)
I think children don't experience mental health problems (Sa tingin ko, ang mga bata ay hindi nakakaranas ng mga problema sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	3.89	0.87	Knowledgeable (K)
I think poor mental health in adolescents is not a major concern because it is typical for them to act out due to hormonal mood swings and attention-seeking behavior (Sa tingin ko, ang kahinaan sa kalusugang pangkaisipan ng mga kabataan ay hindi isang pangunahing alalahanin dahil karaniwan na sa kanila ang kumilos batay sa hormonal mood swings gayundin ang pag-uugaling naghahanap ng atensyon)	3.42	1.20	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
I think people who have a steady source of income and a lot of friends are less likely to develop mental health problems because they have nothing to be depressed about (Sa	3.42	1.13	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)

palagay ko, ang mga taong may matatag na pinagkakakitaan at may maraming kaibigan ay malamang na hindi magkaroon ng mga problema sa kalusugang pangkaisipan dahil wala silang dapat ikabahala)				
I think laziness and gentleness of character contribute to serious mental health issues (Sa tingin ko, ang katamaran at kalumayan ng ugali ay bahagi ng mga seryosong isyu sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	2.48	0.97	Fair Knowledge (FK)	
	Overall Mean	3.82	Knowledgeable (K)	

Table 7 reveals that the respondents are knowledgeable about the risk factors and causes of mental health illnesses, as indicated by an overall mean score of 3.82. The statement “Mental disorders result from both genetic and environmental factors” received the highest mean score of 4.35 with a standard deviation of 0.74. This was closely followed by the statements “Adult mental health can be strongly influenced by childhood trauma, abuse, or neglect” (mean of 4.30 and standard deviation of 0.67), “Alcohol abuse can cause a wide range of mental health problems, including anxiety and depression” (mean of 4.25 and standard deviation of 0.75), and “A head injury or a neurological condition like epilepsy can impact behavior and mood” (mean of 4.14 and standard deviation of 0.70).

These items, along with the statements “People from loving, nurturing homes can also struggle with their mental health” (mean of 4.06 and standard deviation of 0.77), “Mental illness is a prevalent disability in the Philippines” (mean of 3.89 and standard deviation of 0.86), and “Children don’t experience mental health problems” (mean of 3.89 and standard deviation of 0.87), all fell into the 'Knowledgeable' category.

Statements such as “Poor mental health in adolescents is not a major concern because it is typical for them to act out due to hormonal mood swings and attention-seeking behavior” and “People who have a steady source of income and a lot of friends are less likely to develop mental health problems because they have nothing to be depressed about” both received a mean score of 3.42 with standard deviations of 1.20 and 1.13, respectively, placing them in the 'Moderately Knowledgeable' category. Lastly, the statement “Laziness and gentleness of character contribute to serious mental health issues” received the lowest mean score of 2.48 and a standard deviation of 0.97, indicating 'Fair Knowledge'.

The findings of this study align with previous research conducted by Simon & Mahinay (2023) and Dizon (2019), which found that respondents have a good understanding of the causes and risk factors associated with mental health problems.

Interestingly, respondents of the present study recognized that mental disorders stem from an interplay of genetic and environmental factors. This is consistent with the 2019 study by Dizon, which found that participants recognized that alterations in brain function could trigger mental disorders. However, this contradicts the earlier research by Jorm et al. (2000), which indicated that the public tends to ignore the biomedical origins of mental illness, signifying that there is a potential improvement in mental health literacy over time.

However, when it came to detailed knowledge of risk factors and causes of mental health illnesses, the respondents' understanding was significantly less compared to other areas of mental health literacy, reflected in the lower mean score for this particular subscale. This observation aligns with the research findings of Publico (2020) and Satparam (2023) who identified that the lowest-scoring domain in mental health literacy was the understanding of risk factors and causes of mental health illnesses. Publico (2020) reasoned that this is likely because the information related to this domain is often highly technical and filled with medical jargon, making it more challenging for non-medical professionals to fully grasp.

Intriguingly, items that scored lower in this domain are not on the medical aspect but predominantly related to socio-cultural misconceptions about mental health. One such misconception is the belief that individuals with a stable income and a strong social network are less prone to mental health issues. This belief stems from the oversimplified view that these individuals seemingly have no reason to be depressed. However, this perspective neglects the complex nature of mental health, which can be influenced by many factors beyond one’s financial status or social standing.

Another misconception, the least understood, is the idea that certain personality traits, such as laziness or gentleness, can lead to severe mental health problems. This perception is rooted in societal stereotypes and stigmatization associated with mental health, leading to the erroneous belief that mental health problems are character flaws rather than legitimate medical conditions.

This misunderstanding might also be linked to the cultural emphasis on resilience and self-sufficiency among Filipinos, viewing the capacity to overcome one’s emotional challenges as a personal duty (Martinez et al., 2020). Being resilient, however, doesn't mean one should neglect their own feelings or bear their problem alone; in fact, acknowledging and accepting one’s struggle with mental health is a sign of strength.

Knowledge of Self-Treatment

The knowledge of self-treatment refers to the understanding and application of strategies that individuals can use to manage or improve their mental health. This may include living a healthy lifestyle which covers working out, eating a balanced diet, and getting enough sleep as well as practicing mindfulness and relaxation, building and maintaining meaningful relationships, and knowing when to seek professional help, among others.

Table 8. Knowledge of Self-Treatment

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
I think getting quality sleep and rest can help in managing emotions (Sa tingin ko, makakatulong ang pagkakaroon ng tulog at pamamahinga upang mapangalagaan ang emosyon)	4.59	0.52	Very Knowledgeable (VK)
I think exercise and other forms of physical activity can help improve one's mood and reduce anxiety (Sa tingin ko ang ehersisyo at iba pang pampisikal na aktibidad ay makakatulong na mapabuti ang mood ng isang tao at mabawasan ang pagkabalisa)	4.59	0.52	Very Knowledgeable (VK)
I think a strong social network with family or friends would be helpful in dealing with life's challenges (Sa tingin ko ang pagkakaroon ng matibay na relasyon sa pamilya at mga kaibigan ay makakatulong sa pagharap sa mga hamon ng buhay)	4.57	0.59	Very Knowledgeable (VK)
I think relaxation exercises like meditation and mindfulness can improve your state of mind and outlook in life (Sa tingin ko, ang mga ehersisyong nakakarelaks gaya ng pagbubulay-bulay ay nakapagpapabuti sa daloy ng kaisipan at pananaw sa buhay)	4.51	0.56	Very Knowledgeable (VK)
I think accepting your flaws and treating yourself with kindness is a helpful coping strategy (Sa tingin ko ang pagtanggap sa iyong mga kapintasan at mabuting pagtrato sa iyong sarili ay pamamaraang sadyang nakakatulong)	4.50	0.60	Very Knowledgeable (VK)
I think taking time for your hobbies is a helpful self-care strategy (Sa tingin ko, ang paglalaan ng oras para sa iyong mga libangan ay isang kapaki-pakinabang na pamamaraan upang mapangalagaan ang sarili)	4.48	0.56	Knowledgeable (K)
I think healthy eating habits can improve your mental health (Sa tingin ko ang nakagawiang pagkain ng masustansya ay makakapagabuti sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	4.45	0.64	Knowledgeable (K)
I think recognizing and confronting your issues would be beneficial in dealing with mental health problems (Sa tingin ko, ang pagkilala at pagharap sa mga isyu ay magiging kapaki-pakinabang sa pagharap sa mga problemang kaugnay sa kalusugan pangkaisipan)	4.37	0.67	Knowledgeable (K)
I think temporary isolation or break from activities or situations causing anxiety helps in managing emotions (Sa tingin ko, ang pansamantalang paghihiwalay o pagpapahinga sa mga aktibidad o sitwasyon na nakapagpapadulot ng pagkabalisa ay nakakatulong na maisaayos ang emosyon)	4.36	0.70	Knowledgeable (K)
I think setting unrealistic goals and sticking to a strict schedule will only keep you motivated and moving forward in life (Sa palagay ko, ang pagtatakda ng mga hindi makatotohanang layunin at ang pagsunod sa isang mahigpit na iskedyul ay patuloy na makapanghihikayat at makapagpapasulong sa iyong buhay)	3.20	1.24	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
Overall Mean	4.36		Knowledgeable (K)

Table 8 indicates that the respondents were knowledgeable on self-treatment of mental health problems, as reflected by an overall mean score of 4.36. The strategies that received the highest mean scores, interpreted as 'very knowledgeable', were getting quality sleep and rest can help in managing emotions and exercise and other forms of physical activity can help improve one's mood and reduce anxiety, both with a mean of 4.59 and an SD of 0.52.

Other strategies that were highly rated and interpreted as knowledgeable include maintaining a strong social network with family or friends (mean of 4.57 and SD of 0.59), practicing relaxation exercises like meditation and mindfulness (mean of 4.51 and SD of 0.56), and accepting personal flaws and treating oneself with kindness (mean of 4.50 and SD of 0.60). Strategies such as taking time for hobbies (mean of 4.48 and SD of 0.56), maintaining healthy eating habits (mean of 4.45 and SD of 0.64), recognizing and confronting personal issues (mean of 4.37 and SD of 0.67), and temporarily isolating oneself from anxiety-inducing activities or situations (mean of 4.36 and SD of 0.70) were also rated as 'knowledgeable'.

On the other hand, the strategy of "setting unrealistic goals and sticking to a strict schedule will only keep you motivated and moving forward in life" received the lowest mean of 3.20 and an SD of 0.42, indicating a 'moderately knowledgeable' understanding.

Among all subscales of mental health literacy, knowledge on self-treatment received the highest overall mean in this study, suggesting that respondents are most knowledgeable in this domain. This finding aligns with Dizon's (2019) study on students in a state university but contradicts Satparam's (2023) study on Teacher Education Faculty, which ranked it in the bottom two. This discrepancy may be explained by the fact that Dizon's study focused on a younger demographic, who often have greater exposure to mental health information due to education, media, and online resources, as opposed to Satparam who concentrated his study on an older generation.

Since the introduction of the Employee Assistance Program in 2018, the HRDMO has been consistently offering seminars and training sessions on wellness. These sessions cover a variety of topics, including mental health awareness, mental health in the workplace, work-life balance, psychological first aid, stress debriefing and management, mindfulness, enhancing mental health through diet and nutrition, spiritual care, and active stress coping strategies in the workplace. In addition to these, the institution also offers wellness programs like Zumba and yoga, distributes self-care kits, and shares infographics on maintaining mental health. These efforts may have

collectively contributed to the promotion of mental health literacy, particularly on self-treatment, among the employees as evidenced by the results in this domain.

However, the respondents' understanding of the significance of goal setting in mental health appears to be moderate, as evidenced by the lower mean score for the item "setting unrealistic goals and sticking to a strict schedule." It implies that the respondents might not fully recognize that while discipline and goal setting are crucial elements in maintaining mental health, they should be counterbalanced with flexibility and a realistic outlook. Setting goals that are too ambitious or adhering to an overly strict schedule can lead to additional stress and anxiety. This is because when these lofty goals are not met, it can lead to feelings of failure and inadequacy. Similarly, a rigid schedule can create a high-pressure environment that leaves little room for relaxation and self-care, which are also essential for mental health. This misunderstanding could be a result of societal pressures, where success is often equated with constant productivity and achievement. This "rise and grind" mentality can create an environment where individuals feel compelled to push themselves beyond their limits, often at the expense of their mental well-being.

Knowledge of Where to Seek Information

Knowledge of where to seek information refers to the understanding of where and how to find relevant information regarding mental health. This could include books, journals, internet platforms, educational events, and professionals, among others.

Table 9. Knowledge of Where to Seek Information

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description
I think I know how to use the internet in seeking information about mental health (Sa tingin ko alam kong gamitin ang internet sa paghahanap ng impormasyon tungkol sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	4.14	0.77	Knowledgeable (K)
I think I have friends and family members who can help me in my search for information about mental health (Sa tingin ko may mga kaibigan at kapamilya akong makakatulong sa akin sa paghahanap ng impormasyon tungkol sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	4.08	0.85	Knowledgeable (K)
I think that there are professional organizations (Philippine Mental Health Association, Psychological Association of the Philippines, Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association, etc.) that I can reach through social media to seek information on mental health (Sa tingin ko may mga organisasyong pampropesyonal (Philippine Mental Health Association, Psychological Association of the Philippines, Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association, atbp.) na maaari kong maabot sa pamamagitan ng social media upang humingi ng impormasyon tungkol sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	3.94	0.86	Knowledgeable (K)
I think there is a widespread mental health information campaign on social media (Sa tingin ko may malawakang pangangampanya ng impormasyon sa kalusugang pangkaisipan sa social media (hal. Facebook))	3.86	0.86	Knowledgeable (K)
I think TSU HRDMO doesn't provide trainings and seminars on professional health and well-being where I can learn about mental health (Sa tingin ko ang TSU HRDMO ay hindi nagbibigay ng mga training at seminar tungkol sa propesyonal na kalusugan at kagalingan kung saan maaari kong matutunan ang tungkol sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	3.82	1.02	Knowledgeable (K)
I think I cannot find mental health information in books and journals available in libraries and bookstores (Sa tingin ko hindi ako makakahanap ng mga impormasyong tungkol sa kalusugan pangkaisipan sa mga aklat at dyornal na makukuha sa mga silid-aklatan at bookstore)	3.65	0.94	Knowledgeable (K)
I think that I can contact the Department of Health via email, Facebook, and Messenger for inquiries on mental health (Sa tingin ko maaari akong makipag- ugnayan sa Kagawaran ng Kalusugan sa pamamagitan ng email, Facebook, at Messenger para sa mga katanungan tungkol sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	3.55	0.93	Knowledgeable (K)
I think there are barangay health centers nearby where I can go for information on mental health (Sa tingin ko may mga malalapit na barangay health center kung saan maaari akong makapangalap ng mga impormasyon tungkol sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	3.33	1.05	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
I think there are no there are support groups in my community that can aid me as I explore mental health issues (Sa tingin ko walang grupo sa aking komunidad na makakatulong sa aking pag-aaral tungkol sa mga sakit sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	3.26	1.08	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
I think I don't know where to seek information about mental health (Sa tingin ko hindi ko malalaman ang paghahanapan ng impormasyon tungkol sa kalusugang pangkaisipan)	3.24	1.15	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
Overall Mean	3.69		Knowledgeable (K)

As indicated by Table 9, the respondents demonstrated a strong understanding of where to find information on mental health issues, with an overall mean score of 3.69, interpreted as Knowledgeable. The statement "I believe I know how to use the internet to find information about mental health" received the highest mean score of 4.14 and standard deviation of .77. This was closely followed by

“I believe I have friends and family members who can assist me in finding information about mental health” with a mean of 4.08 and standard deviation of .85. Other statements such as “I believe there are professional organizations (Philippine Mental Health Association, Psychological Association of the Philippines, Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association, etc.) that I can access via social media for mental health information” with a mean of 3.94 and standard deviation of .86, and “I believe there is a widespread mental health information campaign on social media” with a mean of 3.86 and standard deviation of .86, were also rated as Knowledgeable.

Statements like “I believe TSU HRDMO doesn’t offer training and seminars on professional health and well-being where I can learn about mental health” with a mean of 3.82 and standard deviation of 1.02, and “I believe I cannot find mental health information in books and journals available in libraries and bookstores” with a mean of 3.65 and standard deviation of .94, were also interpreted Knowledgeable. The statement “I believe I can contact the Department of Health via email, Facebook, and Messenger for mental health inquiries” had a mean of 3.55 and a standard deviation of .93, also falling under the Knowledgeable category.

Statements such as “I believe there are barangay health centers nearby where I can go for information on mental health” with a mean of 3.33 and standard deviation of 1.05, and “I believe there are no support groups in my community that can assist me as I explore mental health issues” with a mean of 3.26 and standard deviation of 1.08, along with the lowest mean of 3.24 and standard deviation of 1.15 for the statement “I believe I don’t know where to seek information about mental health”, were all categorized as Moderately Knowledgeable.

The data suggests that respondents are most confident seeking mental health information online and from personal networks, and less confident in local resources and traditional sources such as books and journals. Respondents’ preference to use the internet for information seeking can be attributed to the reduced stigma and anxiety it offers. According to an online psychological service provider, the anonymity that the internet provides can make people feel more comfortable expressing themselves, making it an attractive platform for those who may feel stigmatized or anxious in face-to-face interactions. Building on this point, the internet’s accessibility and convenience further enhance its appeal, especially considering that Filipinos have a high level of functional literacy among internet users, recorded at 97.1% (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2020).

Likewise, the reliance on close family and friends for mental health information, as shown by the data, reflects deeply ingrained cultural values. In many cultures, there is a strong adherence to cultural norms and traditions, which often includes seeking information from trusted personal networks before consulting external sources. Moreover, family and friends are not only readily accessible sources of support, but they also offer a level of comfort and familiarity, making them a practical choice for many individuals. These factors, when coupled with practical considerations such as ease of access and comfort level, position personal networks as a preferred source of mental health information (Martinez et al., 2020).

The results also suggest that respondents are generally aware that the institution provides seminar and trainings related to professional health and well-being where they can learn about mental health. However, it seems there is a perceived lack of community support that can help them explore mental health issues. It is observable that accessing mental health care, particularly at the community level, poses significant challenges due to the unavailability of facilities and the lack of mental health awareness among many barangay health workers.

Knowledge of Available Professional Help

The knowledge of available professional help refers to the respondents’ understanding and awareness of various professional resources and services that may help them with their mental health concerns. It also requires recognizing when and how to use these resources.

Table 10. *Knowledge of Available Professional Help*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
I think counseling is the delivery of assistance and guidance by a trained professional in resolving personal, social, or psychological problems and difficulties (Sa tingin ko, ang pagbibigay ng payo ay paghahatid ng tulong at patnubay mula sa isang sinanay na propesyonal upang malutas ang mga personal, panlipunan, o sikolohikal na mga problema at kahirapan)	4.37	0.68	Knowledgeable (K)
I think a mental health professional may refer a client to other professionals to be of better help, with his/her consent (Sa tingin ko, ang isang propesyonal sa kalusugang pangkaisipan ay maaaring ipasangguni ang isang kliyente sa ibang propesyonal upang mas makatulong, datapwat nararapat na may kapahintulutan)	4.23	0.81	Knowledgeable (K)
I think any TSU employee at risk or identified to have a mental health condition may apply for the necessary number of days of leave upon written advice by the University Medical Officer or the accredited physician (Sa tingin ko, ang sinumang empleyado ng TSU na nanganganib o natukoy na may kondisyon sa kalusugang pangkaisipan ay maaaring humiling para sa kinakailangang araw ng pagliban na nakabatay sa payo na pirmado ng University Medical Officer o ng akreditadong doctor)	4.20	0.72	Knowledgeable (K)

I think drug abuse is a mental health problem and that there are treatment facilities available in the community (Sa tingin ko, ang pag-abuso sa droga ay isang problema sa kalusugang pangkaisipan at may mga pasilidad sa komuninad na magagamit upang ito ay magamot)	4.13	0.85	Knowledgeable (K)
I think Tarlac State University through the Human Resource Development and Management Office offers counseling among other mental health services for its employees (Sa tingin ko, ang Tarlac State University sa pamamagitan ng Human Resource Development and Management Office ay nagbibigay ng mga serbisyong pangkalusugan kaisipan para sa mga empleyado katulad ng pagpapamatnubay)	4.12	0.78	Knowledgeable (K)
I think employee counseling is not only available through in-person sessions but also over the phone (telecounseling) (Sa tingin ko, ang pagbibigay ng payo sa empleyado ay hindi lamang maisasakatuparan sa pamamagitan ng mga personal na sesyon kundi pati na rin sa telepono (telecounseling))	4.05	0.85	Knowledgeable (K)
I think any TSU employee at risk or identified to have a mental health condition may be accommodated through an adaptable and flexible work arrangements (Sa tingin ko, ang sinumang empleyado ng TSU na nanganganib o natukoy na may kondisyon sa kalusugang pangkaisipan ay maaaring kalingain sa pamamagitan ng mga akma at flexible na gawain)	4.01	0.79	Knowledgeable (K)
I think the National Mental Health Crisis Hotline is available 24 hours a day, seven days a week (Sa tingin ko, ang National Mental Health Crisis Hotline ay maaaring tawagan anumang oras at araw)	3.71	0.90	Knowledgeable (K)
I think people with mental health issues are protected from stigma and discrimination in the workplace under the Mental Health Act (Sa tingin ko, ang mga taong may mga isyu sa kalusugang pangkaisipan ay protektado mula sa stigma at diskriminasyon sa trabaho sa ilalim ng Mental Health Act)	3.70	0.96	Knowledgeable (K)
I think people with psychosocial and mental disabilities can not apply for a Persons with Disabilities (PWD) ID and receive at least a 20% discount on medical services and medication purchases, among other privileges and incentives (Sa tingin ko, ang mga taong may psychosocial at mental na kapansanan ay hindi maaaring mag-aplay para sa isang Persons with Disabilities (PWD) ID at makatanggap ng hindi bababa sa 20% na diskwento sa mga serbisyong medikal at pagbili ng gamot, bukod sa iba pang mga pribilehiyo at insentibo)	3.43	1.29	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
	Overall Mean	4.00	Knowledgeable (K)

Table 10 demonstrates that the respondents were knowledgeable about available professional help, as evidenced by an overall mean score of 4.00. The statement, "Counseling is the delivery of assistance and guidance by a trained professional in resolving personal, social, or psychological problems and difficulties," received the highest mean score of 4.37 and a standard deviation of .68. This was closely followed by the understanding that a mental health professional may refer a client to other professionals for better assistance, with the client's consent. This had a mean score of 4.23 and a standard deviation of .81.

The awareness that any employee at Tarlac State University (TSU) at risk or identified to have a mental health condition may apply for the necessary number of days of leave upon written advice by the University Medical Officer or the accredited physician was also high. This had a mean score of 4.20 and a standard deviation of .72. The recognition that drug abuse is a mental health problem and that there are treatment facilities available in the community had a mean score of 4.13 and a standard deviation of .85. The knowledge that TSU offers counseling among other mental health services for its employees through the Human Resource Development and Management Office had a mean score of 4.12 and a standard deviation of .78.

The understanding that employee counseling is available not only through in-person sessions but also over the phone (telecounseling) had a mean score of 4.0 and a standard deviation of 0.85. The understanding that any TSU employee at risk or identified to have a mental health condition may be accommodated through adaptable and flexible work arrangements had a mean score of 4.01 and a standard deviation of .79. The awareness of the availability of the National Mental Health Crisis Hotline 24 hours a day, seven days a week, and that people with mental health issues are protected from stigma and discrimination in the workplace under the Mental Health Act, had mean scores of 3.71 and 3.70, and standard deviations of .90 and .96, respectively. These are all interpreted as knowledgeable.

The statement that received the lowest mean score of 3.43 and a standard deviation of 1.29, interpreted as moderately knowledgeable, was, "People with psychosocial and mental disabilities cannot apply for a Persons with Disabilities (PWD) ID and receive at least a 20% discount on medical services and medication purchases, among other privileges and incentives."

The results reflect a high level of knowledge about available professional help for mental health issues among the respondents. Specifically, they seem to have a clear understanding of the role of counseling and the process of referral to other professionals for better assistance. They are aware of the support provided by their workplace, Tarlac State University, in terms of leave provisions, flexible working arrangements, and counseling services. They also understand the rights and protections for people with mental health issues under the Mental Health Act. This awareness can be attributed to the university's proactive approach in discussing these services during employee onboarding programs and mental health-related seminars. Furthermore, the respondents' recognition of drug abuse as a mental health issue and their awareness of the community's treatment facilities likely stem from the regular drug prevention

seminars conducted by the university.

However, a knowledge gap becomes apparent when it comes to the applicability of Republic Act No. 7277, also known as the “Magna Carta for Disabled Persons,” to individuals with mental health conditions. The respondents seem to have only moderate knowledge that this act expressly recognizes persons with psychosocial and mental abilities as eligible to receive benefits under the Persons with Disabilities (PWD) Act. This gap may be due to the prevailing misconception that psychosocial and mental abilities do not constitute a valid disability.

Analyzing these findings, it has been determined that respondents have more than adequate knowledge of available professional services, even though, as discussed in previous chapters, employee counseling services are underutilized. This suggests that the issue may not be their awareness, but rather their attitudes toward seeking and receiving professional help.

The reluctance to seek professional mental health assistance among respondents, particularly in the context of the Philippines, may be attributed to a combination of cultural, social, and personal factors. Firstly, there is a strong preference for seeking help from close personal networks such as family and friends (Ines, 2019), (Dizon, 2019), (Simon & Mahinay, 2023), and (Que-Legaspi, Reyes & Datu, 2014). This is due to the deeply ingrained cultural values that emphasize the importance of familial bonds and friendships. These personal networks are seen as more understanding, trustworthy, and culturally sensitive, making them the first point of contact for many individuals facing mental health challenges. Secondly, there is a perception that mental health professionals are strangers, making it difficult for individuals to express themselves and share their problems (Tuliao, 2014).

This is compounded by the belief that emotional issues are transient and relationship-related, leading to the assumption that these issues can be resolved by talking to friends, family, or trusted community members (Hechanova et al., 2011). Lastly, there is a prevalent misconception that consulting mental health experts is an admission of insanity, or it could potentially tarnish the family’s reputation (Hechanova & Waelde, 2017). This stigma can be even more pronounced in this situation where the professional source is also a part of the organization’s management, particularly, the employee counselor who is also the head of the Human Resources Development and Management Office. In this case, employees may have feared that discussing their mental health concerns could have negatively affected their employment or future opportunities within the organization.

Attitudes that Promote Recognition or Appropriate Help-seeking Behavior

The attitudes that promote recognition and appropriate help-seeking behavior refer to the mindset and empathic understanding that encourages individuals to recognize their own or other’s mental health issues and actively seek professional help.

Table 11. *Attitudes that Promote Recognition or Appropriate Help-seeking Behavior*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
I think mental illness is not a real medical illness (Sa tingin ko ang sakit sa kaisipan ay hindi isang tunay na sakit pangmedikal)	3.94	1.02	Knowledgeable (K)
I think it is best to avoid people with a mental illness so that you don't develop this problem (Sa tingin ko, makabubuting lumayo sa mga taong may sakit sa pag-iisip upang makaiwas sa mga ganitong problema)	3.86	1.06	Knowledgeable (K)
I am willing to make friends with someone who lives with a mental illness (Tinatanggap kong makipagkaibigan sa sinumang may sakit sa kaisipan)	3.82	0.73	Knowledgeable (K)
I am willing to supervise a colleague who has a history of mental illness (Handa akong subaybayan ang isang kasamahan na nakaranas ng sakit sa kaisipan)	3.76	0.79	Knowledgeable (K)
I think seeing a mental health professional means you are not strong enough to manage your own difficulties (Sa tingin ko, ang pagpapatangin sa isang propesyonal sa kalusugan ng kaisipan ay nangangahulugan na hindi sapat ang sariling kakayahan upang paglabanan ang nararanasang hirap)	3.60	1.20	Knowledgeable (K)
I am willing to have someone with a mental illness work closely with me on a job (Handa akong makatrabaho ng malapitan ang isang taong may sakit sa kaisipan)	3.54	0.79	Knowledgeable (K)
I think people with mental illness are dangerous (Sa tingin ko ang mga taong may sakit sa pag-iisip ay mapanganib)	3.46	1.07	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
I think mental illness is a sign of personal weakness (Sa tingin ko ang sakit sa kaisipan ay tanda ng sariling kahinaan)	3.38	1.23	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
I am willing to work with a supervisor who has a history of mental illness (Tinatanggap kong makasama sa trabaho ang isang superbisor na may sakit sa kaisipan)	3.21	0.92	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
I am willing to have someone who has a mental illness marry into my family (Tanggap kong maikasal sa aking kapamilya ang isang taong may sakit sa kaisipan)	2.93	0.90	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
Overall Mean	3.55		Knowledgeable (K)

Table 11 reveals that respondents exhibited knowledgeable attitudes towards mental health, with an overall mean of 3.55. The statement “I think mental illness is not a real medical illness” recorded the highest mean of 3.94 and a standard deviation of 1.02, indicating a

strong understanding of mental health as a legitimate medical condition. This was closely followed by the statement “I think it is best to avoid people with a mental illness so that you don’t develop this problem” with a mean of 3.86 and a standard deviation of 1.06, and “I am willing to make friends with someone who lives with a mental illness” with a mean of 3.82 and a standard deviation of .73.

Other statements such as “I am willing to supervise a colleague who has a history of mental illness”, “I think seeing a mental health professional means you are not strong enough to manage your own difficulties”, and “I am willing to have someone with a mental illness work closely with me on a job” had means of 3.76, 3.60, and 3.54 and a standard deviation of .79, 1.20, and .79 respectively, further demonstrating a knowledgeable attitude. However, some statements reflected a moderately knowledgeable attitude. For instance, “I think people with mental illness are dangerous” had a mean of 3.46 and a standard deviation of 1.07, “I think mental illness is a sign of personal weakness” had a mean of 3.38 and a standard deviation of 1.23, “I am willing to work with a supervisor who has a history of mental illness” had a mean of 3.21 and a standard deviation of .92, and “I am willing to have someone who has a mental illness marry into my family” had the lowest mean of 2.93 and a standard deviation of .90.

These findings align with the high literacy on disorder recognition previously discussed in this chapter. Respondents demonstrated an informed attitude towards mental health issues, as evidenced by high mean scores in recognizing that mental illness is a valid medical condition and understanding that it is not contagious. They also expressed empathy and willingness to form friendships, work closely with, and supervise individuals with a mental illness.

Despite these positive attitudes, this domain, focusing on attitudes promoting the recognition of mental health issues or encouraging appropriate help-seeking behavior, recorded the lowest mean score among all domains of mental health literacy. This observation supports the studies of Dizon (2019) and Cardinez & Mahinay (2023), who concluded that respondents harbor misconceptions and stereotypes about mental health problems.

In the present study, items related to stigma and misconceptions, such as the belief that mental illness is a sign of personal weakness and that people with mental illness are dangerous, scored low. These misconceptions, possibly stemming from lack of awareness, cultural beliefs, or societal norms, pose significant barriers to the proper recognition of disorders and willingness to engage in help-seeking behavior. Dizon (2019) suggests that these misunderstandings and stereotypes result in stigma, which primarily manifests in two forms: social stigma and self-stigma. Social stigma, also referred to as public stigma, involves negatively categorizing individuals with mental health problems. This often leads to discrimination.

The results also reflect respondents’ reservations about having a person with a mental illness as their superior, possibly indicating concerns about power dynamics in the workplace or doubts about the capability of individuals with a history of mental illness to assume leadership roles. Furthermore, there seems to be reluctance to accept a person with mental illness marrying into their family. A study by Tanaka et al. in 2018 noted that Filipinos view mental illness as a family issue and a sign of “bad blood”. Given the strong family-oriented culture of Filipinos and their belief that mental health problems are hereditary and transmissible, this could explain their hesitance.

As a whole, while there is a general understanding and empathy towards mental health issues, misconceptions and stigmas persist, highlighting the need for continued education and awareness campaigns to dispel these harmful beliefs.

Comparison of Mental Health Literacy Among Respondents when Grouped According to Profile

The mental health literacy of the respondents was grouped according to their demographic profile, specifically, on age, sex, position, educational attainment, and attendance to mental health-related training. This classification aimed to highlight the differences and similarities among these groups and identify the specific areas of mental health literacy that each group requires further development.

Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Age

Table 12. *Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Age*

Variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Result
Disorder Recognition	Between Groups	2.671	3	0.890	4.343	0.005	Reject Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	42.431	207	0.205				
	Total	45.102	210					
Risk-Factor Knowledge	Between Groups	2.600	3	0.867	4.646	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	38.611	207	0.187				
	Total	41.210	210					
Self-treatment Knowledge	Between Groups	1.101	3	0.367	2.121	0.099	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Within	35.820	207	0.173				

	Groups							
Information-Seeking Knowledge	Total	36.921	210					
	Between Groups	0.391	3	0.130	0.355	0.785	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	76.012	207	0.367				
Available Professional Help	Total	76.403	210					
	Between Groups	0.417	3	0.139	0.620	0.603	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.429	207	0.224				
Attitudes	Total	46.846	210					
	Between Groups	9.870	3	3.290	8.520	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	79.937	207	0.386				
	Total	89.807	210					

The data from Table 12 reveals a significant correlation between the respondents' age and their Mental Health Literacy. This correlation is particularly evident in three domains: the ability to recognize Mental Health Problems ($p=0.005$), the knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes ($p=0.004$), and the attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior ($p=0.000$). Conversely, the domains of self-treatment knowledge ($p=0.099$), information-seeking knowledge ($p=0.785$), and professional help knowledge ($p=0.603$) do not exhibit a significant difference, implying that age may not influence these areas.

The analysis of mental health literacy across different age groups reveals interesting patterns. The highest mean scores for disorder recognition (DR), risk-factor knowledge (RFK), and attitudes were observed in the 23 to 26-year-old age group, suggesting a more comprehensive understanding of mental health issues among this demographic (refer to Appendix B). In contrast, the 43 to 58-year-old group scored the lowest in DR and RFK, while the 59 to 63-year-old group had the least favorable attitudes towards mental health.

These findings could be attributed to several factors. For instance, the 23 to 26-year-olds, often referred to as Gen Z or 'Zoomers', were raised as digital natives and grew up with an abundance of information at their fingertips. They may have been more exposed to content about mental health on social media platforms, attended webinars, or participated in online forums discussing mental health issues, thus, explaining their higher scores in mental health literacy. This observation aligns with a 2019 report by the American Psychological Association, which found that Gen Z is more familiar with mental health concepts and more open to discussing and seeking treatment compared to older generations.

On the other hand, the lower scores among the older age groups, specifically Generation X (aged 43 to 58) and Baby Boomers (aged 59 to 63), could be due to their differing perceptions of mental health. For example, Generation X tends to reserve mental health care for severe situations, such as trauma from war or assault, rather than everyday stressors like divorce or job changes. This tendency could explain their lower literacy in recognizing mental disorders, as well as their understanding of its causes and risk factors. Meanwhile, Baby Boomers, having grown up in an era when mental health issues were stigmatized and rarely discussed openly, may struggle to engage in healthy conversations about mental health, contributing to their less favorable attitudes towards it. (Therapy.com).

The results highlight the profound influence of generational differences and societal norms on mental health literacy. They underscore the necessity of fostering mental health education and facilitating open dialogue across diverse age groups. Furthermore, the differences in perceptions and understanding across generations highlight the necessity for personalized mental health education and outreach programs. This customized strategy ensures that the distinct requirements and viewpoints of each generation are properly addressed.

Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Sex

Table 13. *Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Sex*

Variables	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision	Result
Disorder Recognition	0.405	0.686	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Risk-Factor Knowledge	0.652	0.515	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Self-Treatment Knowledge	0.526	0.600	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Information-Seeking Knowledge	1.265	0.207	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Available Professional Help	1.806	0.072	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Attitudes	.299	0.765	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 13 presents the results of a t-test analysis on the mental health literacy of respondents, according to sex. The analysis reveals no significant differences between males and females across all studied domains. Each subscale yielded a significant value (Sig. 2-tailed)

greater than 0.05, the standard threshold for determining statistical significance. This finding suggests that the respondents' sex does not significantly influence their mental health literacy, encompassing their ability to recognize disorders, knowledge of where to find information, knowledge of risk factors and causes, knowledge of self-treatments, knowledge of professional help available, and attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behaviors.

Interestingly, this statistically insignificant difference between sexes contradicts previous studies, such as those by Lawlor et al., 2008; Reavley et al., 2012; and Clouston et al., 2017, which concluded that females are more mentally literate than males. However, it aligns with recent research by Satparam (2023) on the teacher education faculty of Albay, Philippines.

Despite the similarities in mental health literacy, it's important to note that males and females often face different mental health challenges. Men, for instance, frequently struggle with substance misuse (Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality, 2017), while women are more prone to anxiety, eating disorders, and depression (McLean et al., 2011; Albert, 2015; Striegel-Moore et al., 2010). Women also experience specific types of depression unique to periods of hormonal change, such as perinatal depression, premenstrual dysphoric disorder, and perimenopause-related depression (Chesser et al., 2021). Yet, the suicide rate for men is four times higher than that for women, according to the American Psychological Association (2015).

These disparities can be attributed to socio-cultural factors that differently impact the sexes when seeking help. Traditional gender stereotypes, which expect men to be strong and self-reliant, may deter them from seeking help for mental health issues due to feelings of shame or perceived threats to their masculinity. A study examining the experiences of individuals with depression and suicidal thoughts found that more men than women reported feeling ashamed about seeking professional assistance. Conversely, women often encounter barriers to accessing quality treatment for their physical and mental health. The medical industry's bias towards male symptoms over female symptoms when diagnosing conditions, and its tendency to dismiss female pain or self-reported symptoms as exaggerated or hysterical (Harvard Health Blog, 2017 & The Guardian, 2017), often results in women being misdiagnosed, underdiagnosed, ineffectively treated, or not treated at all.

Nevertheless, in the context of this study, it is inferred that individuals of both sexes exhibit comparable understanding and attitudes on mental health. This could indicate that the participants have been exposed to similar educational or training opportunities related to mental health, have had equivalent experiences with mental health issues, either personally or through their acquaintances, and/or it implies that the institution or community where the study took place did not distinguish between sexes when addressing or managing mental health concerns. Significantly, this observation also highlights the effectiveness of the University's Gender and Development program, reinforcing its role in promoting gender equality in mental health awareness and understanding.

Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Position

Table 14. *Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Position*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Result</i>
Disorder Recognition	1.797	0.074	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Risk-Factor Knowledge	1.378	0.170	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Self-Treatment Knowledge	1.503	0.134	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Information-Seeking Knowledge	1.041	0.299	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Available Professional Help	0.968	0.334	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Attitudes	2.199	0.029	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 14 presents the results of a t-test analysis on the mental health literacy of respondents according to their positions. The results indicate that the differences in mental health literacy across positions are not statistically significant inability to recognize disorders (t-value=1.797, p=0.074), knowledge of risk factors and causes (t-value=1.378, p=0.170), knowledge of where to seek information (t-value=1.041, p=0.299), knowledge of self-treatments (t-value=1.503, p=0.134), and knowledge of professional help available (t-value=0.968, p=0.334). However, for the attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behaviors, the difference is statistically significant (t-value=2.199, p=0.029). This suggests that the position of the respondents significantly influences their attitudes towards mental health.

Among all the subscales of mental health literacy, the only domain where a significant difference was observed when data are categorized based on position is in attitudes that foster recognition and appropriate help-seeking behaviors. As illustrated in Appendix D, the teaching personnel, with a mean score of 3.64, demonstrated higher literacy than the non-teaching staff, who had a mean score of 3.44. This suggests that the teaching personnel, when it comes to attitudes towards mental health, are more literate.

The reasons behind these results are multifaceted. One explanation could be the higher educational attainment of most teaching personnel compared to non-teaching personnel. This disparity might be further exacerbated by the greater availability of training opportunities for faculty. Another contributing factor could be the nature of faculty positions, which might inherently encourage help-seeking behaviors. This inclination could stem from their frequent exposure to students' mental health issues and their integral responsibility for students' well-being, a responsibility not typically shared by non-teaching personnel. Yet another plausible

explanation is the influence of the organization's culture and policies around mental health. These factors might exert a more profound impact on attitudes than on knowledge. For instance, the workplace environment among teachers might have been more empathetic and supportive, thereby encouraging appropriate help-seeking behaviors more than on non-teaching staff.

These findings underscore the importance of considering the role of position within an organization when addressing mental health literacy and attitudes. This suggests that targeted interventions or training, particularly aimed at promoting a proper attitude toward mental health among non-teaching staff, would be beneficial.

Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Educational Attainment

Table 15. *Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Education*

Variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Result
Disorder Recognition	Between Groups	1.265	4	0.316	1.487	0.207	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	43.837	206	0.213				
	Total	45.102	210					
Risk-Factor Knowledge	Between Groups	2.207	4	0.552	2.915	0.022	Reject Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	39.003	206	0.189				
	Total	41.210	210					
Self-treatment Knowledge	Between Groups	1.252	4	0.313	1.808	0.129	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.669	206	0.173				
	Total	36.921	210					
Available Professional Help	Between Groups	1.567	4	0.392	1.782	0.134	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	45.279	206	0.220				
	Total	46.846	210					
Attitudes	Between Groups	3.745	4	0.936	2.241	0.066	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	86.062	206	0.418				
	Total	89.807	210					

The data from Table 15 reveal the correlation between the respondents' educational attainment and their Mental Health Literacy. No significant differences were observed in the domains of the ability to recognize Mental Health Problems ($p=0.207$), self-treatment knowledge ($p=0.129$), professional help knowledge ($p=0.134$), and attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior ($p=0.066$). However, significant differences were recorded in the knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes ($p=0.022$) and information-seeking knowledge ($p=0.009$). This suggests that the educational attainment of the respondents significantly influences these domains of mental health.

Building upon this, the study uncovers a significant pattern among respondents when categorized by their educational attainment. It was observed that respondents with doctorate degrees recorded the highest mean scores in the domains of 'Knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes' and 'Information-Seeking Knowledge'. In contrast, the lowest scores were found among those with only an elementary education (refer to Appendix E). This suggests that higher educational attainment correlates with increased literacy in these domains.

This observation aligns with the study conducted by Rey et al., (2022) among adults in Metro Manila. The study found that adults with higher education were more likely to recognize mental illness, be aware of available support, and understand how mental health is influenced. This implies that individuals with more education are better equipped to identify mental health conditions in themselves or others. They might be more aware of symptoms like persistent sadness or excessive worry, more knowledgeable about where to find help, such as counseling services or mental health hotlines, and understand that several factors, like stress or life events, can impact mental health.

This correlation can be contextualized within the broader academic discourse. Research has demonstrated a robust and positive correlation between completed education and adults' mental health (Halpern-Manners, 2016). Higher levels of education are believed to enhance people's skills and develop better-coping mechanisms, leading to improved mental health literacy. This could be because higher education often involves learning problem-solving skills and coping strategies. For instance, someone with a university degree might have learned stress management techniques during their studies, which they can apply in their daily life.

Moreover, education often leads to better economic resources, like a higher income or more wealth (Zimmerman & Woolf, 2014). This could mean that people with more education are more likely to afford mental health services or live in areas with better access to such services. Education also tends to lead to better social resources, like access to supportive social networks. This could mean that people with more education have more friends or colleagues whom they can turn to for financial, informational, emotional, and psychological support.

As a whole, the results underscore the pivotal role of education in enhancing mental health literacy. It further proposes that specialized interventional and educational programs could be specifically designed for individuals with lower educational attainment. Furthermore, it emphasizes the need for ongoing efforts to improve educational opportunities to promote mental health literacy and, ultimately, improve mental health outcomes.

Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Training Attendance

Table 16. *Mental Health Literacy of Respondents According to Training Attendance*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Result</i>
Disorder Recognition	2.421	0.016	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Risk-Factor Knowledge	3.667	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Self-Treatment Knowledge	3.019	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
Information-Seeking Knowledge	4.939	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Available Professional Help	5.406	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Attitudes	3.608	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 16 provides an analysis of the t-test results on the mental health literacy of respondents, based on their participation in mental health-related training. The findings reveal that, apart from the ability to recognize Mental Health Problems (t -value=2.421, p =0.016), there are statistically significant differences in mental health literacy across all domains between respondents who have attended mental health-related training and those who have not. Specifically, the following domains exhibited significant differences: knowledge of risk factors and causes (t -value=3.667, p =.000), knowledge of self-treatments (t -value=3.019, p =.003), knowledge of where to seek information (t -value=4.939, p =0.000), knowledge of professional help available (t -value=5.406, p =0.000), and attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking (t -value=3.608, p =0.000). These findings suggest that participation in training significantly influences respondents' mental health literacy positively.

The compelling results of this analysis underscore training's effectiveness in strengthening participants' mental health literacy. As highlighted by Lacerenza et al. (2017), internal or on-site training programs often yield more substantial organizational outcomes compared to their external or off-site counterparts. This can be attributed to the customization inherent in internal training, which caters to the specific needs and culture of the organization.

In this context, it appears that the mental health-related training provided by the institution has been instrumental in imparting a comprehensive understanding of mental health issues. This includes knowledge of risk factors, self-treatment, and available professional help. Moreover, these training programs have provided structured guidance on information-seeking, recognition of mental health problems, and appropriate response strategies. Consequently, this has fostered improved attitudes that encourage recognition and appropriate help-seeking behaviors, making the transition from training to enhanced mental health literacy both evident and impactful. However, this also highlights the need to enhance the programs that promote the understanding of common mental disorders, their symptoms, signs, and treatments to strengthen the disorder recognition domain among the respondents' mental health literacy.

These results attest to the effectiveness of internal training programs in enhancing mental health literacy, thereby emphasizing the value of such initiatives within an organizational context. These programs' success lies in customization, allowing the training provider to address the organization's specific needs and culture. This further suggests that a generic approach may not be as effective in addressing mental health issues within an organization.

Conclusions

In light of the findings, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The respondents are generally knowledgeable across all domains of mental health literacy, as reflected in the overall mean score of 3.92.

The respondents' age, position, education, and training attendance significantly influence certain aspects of their mental health literacy. However, sex does not significantly affect mental health literacy.

Different age groups have varying abilities to recognize mental health problems, understand risk factors and causes, and exhibit attitudes that promote appropriate help-seeking behavior.

The respondents' position within the organization significantly influences their attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-

seeking behaviors.

The respondents' educational attainment significantly affects their knowledge of risk factors and causes, and their information-seeking knowledge.

Attending training related to mental health significantly improves all domains of mental health literacy, except for the ability to recognize mental health problems.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made to enhance the effectiveness of the workplace wellness program of Tarlac State University.

Continued Education: Maintain the elevated level of mental health literacy by continuing to provide educational resources and training.

Enhanced Promotion of Services: Boost employee awareness regarding the University's mental health services by integrating information into onboarding programs, conducting informative seminars, and distributing Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials.

Customized Training Programs and Personalized Mental Health Education: Design and implement training programs tailored to the unique perceptions and understanding of mental health across different demographics. It is recommended to conduct these training sessions in person to ensure participant engagement and to cater to employees who lack digital literacy.

Address Stigma and Socio-Cultural Misconceptions: Work towards debunking socio-cultural misconceptions and dispelling harmful beliefs about mental health.

Bridge the Knowledge Gap: Implement strategies to address the knowledge gap and change attitudes towards seeking professional help. This could involve educational programs, public awareness campaigns, and collaborations with healthcare professionals.

Enhancing Mental Health through Capacity Building: Implement a comprehensive capacity-building program for Heads of Offices/Colleges. This program will empower them with strategies for early detection and prevention of mental health issues. It will focus on effective workload delegation and recognition of early signs of mental health problems, thereby facilitating timely intervention and treatment.

Establishment of Support and Interest Groups: Initiate the formation of support groups, offering a safe space for employees to share their experiences without fear of judgment. Additionally, create interest groups that promote work-life integration. These groups could encompass a variety of areas, including sports, music, literature, arts, and other hobbies. Consider designating a specific time slot, such as every Friday from 5-6 PM, for these club activities.

Enhancement of Facilities: Develop dedicated spaces for club activities and lounges where employees can unwind and socialize during their free time. Additionally, create more conducive environments for counseling sessions to ensure privacy and comfort. These improvements will contribute to a more engaging and supportive workplace.

Evaluation of Working Conditions: Implement a comprehensive review of the working environment, including aspects such as working hours, office dynamics, and workload. Collaborate with union members to ensure workloads are reasonable, particularly for teaching personnel seeking tenure who are juggling responsibilities in research, extension, instruction, and graduate studies.

Strengthening Mental Health Professionals: Implement comprehensive training programs for mental health professionals to enhance their skills and boost their confidence in identifying and addressing mental health issues.

Establishment of an Employee Wellness Unit: Develop a dedicated unit within the Human Resources department, exclusively tasked with overseeing employee wellness. This initiative ensures that the wellness program is not merely an ancillary duty for an existing staff member. Moreover, delegate the role of employee counseling to a specific staff member, diverging from the current practice where the HRDMO director assumes this responsibility. This adjustment will facilitate a more concentrated and efficient administration of both wellness and counseling services.

Establishment of a Mental Health Committee: Form a mental health committee, comprising representatives from every office and college, to guarantee the effective execution of programs. This strategy will not only strengthen the role of mental health professionals but also foster a nurturing environment for all staff members. This ensures that mental health initiatives are tailored to the specific needs of each department and that there is a shared responsibility for mental health across the organization.

Review of Wellness Program: Conduct periodical evaluations on the effectiveness of the wellness program, ensuring alignment with the employees' mental health needs while identifying areas for improvement.

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